

**WORLD LEADER IN GLOBALIZATION
INNOVATION POLICY OF THEIR COUNTRIES**

Usmanov Shokirjon Aliyevich

Assistant of the "Accounting and Banking" department of the Andijan Institute of
Economics and Construction

Abstract: In the article, the place of innovative development in the development of the society, the factors affecting it are disclosed, and current situations are conducted based on the information of local and foreign innovations.

Keywords: Integration, Securities, Capitalization, Funding Sources. Intellectual capital

The second half of the 20th century provided amazing examples of innovative development. Countries that focused on using their advantages in the global innovation arena, and formed their own national, scientific, technical and technological policies, turned out to be competitive.

For most of the last century, the market value of companies was thought to be largely a function of physical assets recorded through accounting statements. But in the 1980s, the Dow Jones (DJIA) index began to show that capitalized assets (buildings, structures, equipment, and inventories) were increasingly diverging from their real value.

If we try to bring all the structural elements to the same denominator, then it becomes clear that these are different types of knowledge.

Thus, a new stage has begun in the development of society, which is characterized by the transition to a new quality of economic growth - "economy of knowledge" or "economy of innovations", taking place under the strong influence of scientific, technical and technological progress, turning knowledge into a global factor of economic development.¹.

Many industrialized countries use such a model, which provides 75-90% of GDP growth, in which economic growth is achieved at the expense of the innovative factor..

At present, it is possible to talk about the development of specific international standards of the concept of innovation as a certain economic category. Innovation is the final result of scientific and creative activity, which is embodied in a new or improved technological process that is sold in the market or, if not, used in practical activities. This allows to distinguish the main properties (criteria) of innovation:

- scientific and technical innovation;
- practical scope (applicability in industry), new, for example: use in industry, agriculture, healthcare, education or other fields of activity;
- it can be implemented for commercial purposes, this means that the innovation is "recognized" by the market, that is, it is sold on the market; this, in turn, means the ability to meet certain consumer demands. This means that no matter

how detailed a new idea is described, formulated and presented in diagrams and drawings, if this idea is not implemented in a product, service or process used in practice, it is not yet considered an innovation (innovation). That is, the important features and criteria of innovation are the novelty of the idea, its embodiment and implementation in practical activities, new products and processes. As long as the new idea is embodied in real objects or processes, it is aimed at meeting the practical needs of people.².

Thus, like the practical embodiment of a new idea in the conditions of a market economy, the integral criterion of innovation is closely related to the criterion of its commercial implementation through the emergence of a new (innovative) product or service on the market.

In general, the scheme of the innovation process can be given as follows:

- The first component of the innovation process - innovations, that is, new ideas, knowledge - is the result of completed scientific (fundamental and practical) research, experimental and constructive developments, and other scientific and technical results.

- The second component of the innovation process is the introduction of works, introduction into practical activity, i.e. innovation and introduction of innovations. - The third component of the innovation process is the diffusion of innovations, that is, previously mastered, used innovations, in other words, the application of innovative products, services or technologies in new places and conditions.

Thus, the concept of "innovation process" is broader than the concept of "innovation", innovation (introduction of news) itself is one of the components of the innovation process.

The transition of the USA, Japan, EU countries to a sustainable development trajectory was achieved based on the expansion of innovative processes in the real sector of the economy. The state innovation policy of one or another country is usually not considered to be a reflection of a certain theoretical model, but it is a composition of activities in different directions, in which it can be noted that national innovation policies have a fundamental identity. (Table № 1).

Table № 1

Directions of national innovation policies of world countries.

Innovation policy directions	Uniqueness	Countries
Optimizing the composition of the national innovation system	<p>Optimizing the state management and planning system in the field of innovation.</p> <p>State financing of science and optimization of the field of innovation</p>	<p>Japan, Norway, Germany</p> <p>USA, Sweden, France, UK, Denmark, Norway, Taiwan, Australia.</p>

	Development of basic research	Great Britain, Sweden, Slovenia
Stimulation of business and science-innovation cooperation within the country	Encourage the symmetrical convergence of science and corporations. Attracting large state investments and national private capital to the field of science and innovation. Stimulation of the innovative activity of the private sector, attracting foreign investments to the innovative sector. Stimulation of the innovative initiative of the scientific sector	USA, Finland Israel, Finland Great Britain, Ireland, China, Korea, India, Israel Germany, Japan, Denmark
Integration into international innovation systems	Complex integration Technological specialization	Finland, Israel, China Korea, Singapore, Taiwan, India
Establish internal innovation systems	Creating special conditions for establishing contacts in the field of innovation.	USA, Norway, Ireland

	Promotion of initiatives of national regions	France, Germany, Finland
Formation of the national innovation system	Restructuring of the public sector of science. Activation of integration of science and education. Involvement of small and medium-sized businesses in the innovation sector. Determination of priority export directions in the field of high technologies	Bulgaria, Poland, Lithuania Latvia, Estonia, Czech Republic Romania, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Turkey Czech Republic, Romania, Chile, Turkey

In order to encourage innovative activity, various incentives and prefects are used in different countries, which are considered very necessary in the adoption of a product with a high science capacity. They operate in the form of flexible, selective, term extensions, tax credits, and accelerated depreciation.

Thus, increasing the country's competitiveness, the most important factor of its development in the direction of effective scientific research cooperation, aimed at creating a favorable economic environment for the implementation of innovative processes (including at the level of regions), is considered as the link between science and production, and the innovative policy of the state. Also, it is very

important to choose the development strategy of the country in the formulation of the innovation policy. Based on this, two main models of state innovation policy can be distinguished:

1. A model aimed at the implementation of scientific and technical programs and projects of national importance, the main goal of which is to stimulate the development of innovative directions of priority for the country.

2. The model aimed at the dissemination of scientific and technical knowledge, the main goal of which is to master new technologies, expand the technological capabilities of economic sectors and industries.

During 2006-2023, a number of measures were taken to improve and finance the scientific-technological base of innovative activities, to expand relations between science and production, state programs for the modernization of economic sectors were adopted, and production localization programs were implemented.

However, in order to draw a conclusion about the contribution of innovations to the development of the competitiveness of our country's economy, the improvement of the level of human development, and the growth of labor productivity, it is necessary to develop a strategic state innovation policy with a full-scale medium and long term on the innovative development of Uzbekistan.

The main economic goal of this innovative policy should be to increase the competitiveness of the national economy and, as a result, to increase the well-being of the population and improve the standard of living.

To achieve this main goal, it is necessary to perform the following tasks:

- to increase the contribution of high-tech sectors in the country's economy, and gradually orient the export policy to the export of products with a higher added value than the export of raw materials;
- creation of innovative and active institutions;
- close cooperation between education, science and business and increasing efficiency of investments in ITTKI;
- general increase in productivity of production factors;
- Increasing investments in human capital to create a "knowledge economy".

In conclusion, it can be noted that most of the state innovation policies in the countries are adopted to solve their national tasks, but at the same time, it is innovation that is appearing as a "new ideology" that unites the entire world community to achieve its set goal and ensure common welfare.

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